

Application of Radioactive Isotopes in the Study of Transition Temperature-II.

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In continuation of our previous work¹, in this line a guest component from carrier-free state to a finite concentration has been under investigation. Same transition temperature has been found in both these extreme concentrations. The study in details gives further support to the findings already arrived at that transition temperature of a guest component can be determined by measuring homogeneous distribution factors (D) at different temperatures with a morphologically analogous host having greater range of stability. It has been found that monoclinic cobalt sulphate exists in two forms like zinc sulphate (monoclinic). Transition temperatures of the two forms of monoclinic cobalt sulphate are respectively $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$, $47^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. The new method has been applied to find out the transition temperatures of thus far unknown orthorhombic $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and that of $3 \text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The transition points have been found to be 18° and 31° respectively.

In the previous investigation¹ it has been shown that transition temperature of a guest component in a mixed crystal forming system where the host has got a bigger range of stability can be determined by the study of homogeneous distribution factor, (D), with a radioactive isotope of the guest at a tracer level. Thus the transition temperature of $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} - 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was determined with Co^{60} as guest and $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host. In view of the fact that the method is such that the component whose transition temperature is to be found out manifests its existence only through mixed crystal formation makes it alluring for determination of the transition temperatures of the metastable phases. Present work refers to the study of transition temperatures of orthorhombic $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and that of zinc sulphate analogue of another variety of monoclinic $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Transition temperature of $3\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ which is thus far unknown has also been the subject matter of study. In distribution measurements in this case $3\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken as host and Mn^{54} was taken as measuring indicator for the guest component. Effect of concentration of the guest component on the nature and extent of uptake from carrier-free state to finite concentration has also been included in the study.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental precautions and techniques were like those already described¹. All the radioactive isotopes namely, carrier-free Co^{58} , Zn^{65} and Mn^{54} as chlorides in dilute hydrochloric acid solution were procured from B.A.R.C., India. A portion of the carrier-free Co^{58} was mixed with a few milligrams of ferric chloride. The solution was made alkaline by adding sodium hydroxide and the precipitated ferric hydroxide containing Co^{58} was washed thoroughly and finally dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid. In case of Mn^{54} a finite quantity of inactive manganous sulphate was added. It was precipitated by adding sodium hydroxide. The precipitate containing Mn^{54} was thoroughly washed. It was finally dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid. A portion of the Zn^{65} activity was thoroughly mixed with a solution containing

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finite quantity of natural zinc sulphate. It was made ammoniacal and zinc was precipitated as sulphide by adding freshly prepared ammonium sulphide solution. The precipitate was washed by centrifugation and dissolved in 0.5N sulphuric acid. Stock solutions containing radioactive isotope thus made were used in the investigations. D was then calculated from the following expression².

$$\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}}\right)_{\text{Solid}} = D \left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}}\right)_{\text{Solution}}$$

A few typical data are given in table-1. Results of the study are shown in figures.

TABLE 1

The distribution of Co⁵⁸, Co⁶⁰, Zn⁶⁵ and Mn⁵⁴ as guest components between preformed hosts like FeSO₄·7H₂O, MgSO₄·7H₂O and 3 CdSO₄·8H₂O

Temperature °C	Host components	Guest components and initial concentrations	Fraction of the host components in the solid phase (%)	Fraction of the tracer in the solid phase (%)	D	
a	10	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	Co ⁶⁰ (1.1 × 10 ⁻³ M)	49.90	44.50	0.805
				40.07	35.96	0.840
				23.85	24.71	0.771
				21.96	18.53	0.808
						Ave. 0.806
b	25	,, ,,	,, ,,	51.00	53.14	1.089
				39.93	38.22	0.931
				30.26	29.70	0.973
				20.78	22.65	1.116
						Ave. 1.027
c	39	FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	Co ⁵⁸ (carrier-free)	50.60	41.80	0.702
				39.96	32.22	0.715
				20.09	15.94	0.759

						Ave. 0.725
d	10	,, ,,	Co ⁶⁰ (1.1 × 10 ⁻³ M)	60.96	49.84	0.637
				49.62	38.16	0.626
				40.83	30.60	0.639
				31.17	21.98	0.622
						Ave. 0.631
e	35	,, ,,	Zn ⁶⁵ (5.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M)	55.30	18.63	0.185
				45.64	14.48	0.202
				34.90	10.98	0.228
				24.43	7.85	0.263
						Ave. 0.219

TABLE I (Contd.)

Temperature °C	Host components	Guest components and initial concentrations	Fraction of the host components in the solid phase (%)	Fraction of the tracer in the solid phase (%)	D	
f	15	3 CdSO ₄ ·8H ₂ O	Mn ⁵⁴	53.40	12.26	0.122
			(1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M)	32.70	8.04	0.180
				26.30	6.10	0.184
			Ave.			0.162
g	35	3 CdSO ₄ ·8H ₂ O	Mn ⁵⁴	50.14	13.66	0.157
			(1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M)	41.20	8.71	0.136
				30.35	6.64	0.163
				22.14	4.81	0.178
Ave.			0.178			
h	7	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	Co ⁶⁰	46.14	40.33	0.789
			(1.1 × 10 ⁻³ M)	47.89	41.56	0.774
				46.16	40.66	0.780
				46.48	40.72	0.791
Ave.			0.783			
i	49	FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	Co ⁶⁰	43.90	38.95	0.816
			(carrier-free)	44.32	39.17	0.808
				43.96	38.32	0.792
				43.76	38.46	0.803
Ave.			0.805			
j	10	,, ,,	Co ⁶⁰	54.45	41.30	0.589
			(1.1 × 10 ⁻³ M)	54.43	41.20	0.587
				55.04	44.00	0.643
				57.35	45.80	0.628
Ave.			0.612			
k	8	,, ,,	Zn ⁶⁵	64.30	19.13	0.131
			(5.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M)	64.86	18.66	0.124
				64.90	18.52	0.123
				65.58	18.73	0.121
Ave.			0.125			
l	20	3 CdSO ₄ ·8H ₂ O	Mn ⁵⁴	40.28	8.07	0.130
			(1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M)	39.54	7.79	0.129
				39.70	7.97	0.131
				40.95	8.91	0.141
Ave.			0.132			

DISCUSSION

Minimum time required for the attainment of equilibrium as is done in this type of investigation¹ has been shown in fig 1 and fig 4, curve B. We have added one more day in the period of equilibration in deriving the values of the distribution factors. It will be of interest to comment that minimum time required in case of carrier-free cobalt is near about the same as was found with Co⁶⁰ containing finite quantities of cobalt¹.

A glance at table 1(a, b) will show that orthorhombic $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ takes up Co^{60} both at 10° and at 25° through mixed crystal formation. Homogeneous distribution factor, (D), comes out constant with carrier-free Co^{58} and $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (c). At lower temperature Co^{60} also forms mixed crystal with $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (d). The constancy of the distribution factor has also been observed at finite concentration with Zn^{65} as guest and $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as the host component (e) both below and above the transition temperature of the guest component. Distribution factor (D) has been found to be constant over wide range of temperature in case of $3\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host and Mn^{54} as guest (Table-1, f, g). Even at such a lower concentration vitriols are found to be mixed crystal forming. Though there is a change in the value of the distribution factor above the transition temperature of the guest component yet the guest components in question are found to be mixed crystal forming above the transition temperature in question.

Fig. 1.—Shows the time required for attainment of equilibrium between hosts and guests. Curve A & B.—Distribution of Co^{60} and Co^{58} between $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals and its saturated solution in 0.5N sulphuric acid at 10° and 39° respectively showing the attainment of equilibrium. Curve C.—Distribution of Co^{60} between $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals and its saturated solution in 0.5N sulphuric acid at 10° showing the attainment of equilibrium.

In view of the fact that statistical error becomes bigger if we take different amount of host components; we equilibrated¹, near about the same amount of host components in a saturated solution of the host incorporated with the guest in question. Each point in the figures (vide fig. 2, fig. 3 and fig. 4, curve A) refer to an average of three or four sets of such computations. A glance at table-1 (h, i, j, k, l) will show the magnitude of errors involved.

In our earlier investigation¹ we added to cobalt activity some amount of natural cobalt. It was of interest to find out the transition temperature with carrier-free cobalt. A glance at fig.2, curve B will show that transition temperature of $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} - 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is the same (47°) as was previously found¹. The values of the partition factor is near about the same as was found with the finite quantities of cobalt. We assume that $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ used in the investigation does not contain any cobalt. Question naturally arises whether higher concentration of the guest components may be employed in the study of transition point so that extent of uptake of the guest can be ascertained by chemical procedures. A glance at fig. 3, curve A will show that transition points found at finite concentration of the guest component (zinc sulphate) and $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host has been the same as were found by working

with Zn^{65} at tracer level¹. It can, therefore, be claimed that by measuring the homogeneous distribution coefficient one can find out the transition temperature even through chemical investigation without using radioactive isotopes in favourable circumstances. Here we rather selected a guest component where partition factor is low. A comparative study of the

Fig. 2.—Study on the transition temperatures of monoclinic and orthorhombic cobalt sulphate.

Curve A.—Describes the distribution values of $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ as host and Co^{60} as guest at different temperatures.

Curve B.—Describes the distribution values of $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ as host and carrier-free Co^{58} as guest component.

Curve C.—Shows the transition temperature of orthorhombic $CoSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O - 6H_2O$ through mixed crystal formation with $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ as host and Co^{60} as guest.

N.B.—Concentrations of ferrous iron and magnesium in the saturated solutions at 35° were $2.15M$ and $3.15M$ respectively and that of natural cobalt was $1.1 \times 10^{-3} M$ in $0.5N H_2SO_4$.

results in the previous investigation¹ will show that distribution factor in each temperature is lower than that at the corresponding temperature at tracer level. This is probably due to the fact that presence of too much of guest component lowered the solubility of the host. In each case ferrous iron left in the solution was found to be less than those found in cases of tracer concentrations of the guest at the temperature in question¹.

Fig. 3.—Study on the transition temperature of monoclinic $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O - 6H_2O$ with $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ as host and Zn^{65} as guest at different concentrations of the guest in $0.5N H_2SO_4$

Curve A.—Refers to study where the concentration of natural zinc was $5.0 \times 10^{-1}M$.

Curve B.—Describes our study where natural zinc concentration was $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$.

A glance at fig. 2, curve C where partition values of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (orthorhombic) as host and Co^{60} as guest has been plotted will show a prominent change at the neighbourhood of 18° . The partition values at temperatures above 18° show the particular characteristic trend of describing a straight line parallel to the temperature axis¹.

It can, therefore, be concluded that transition temperature of orthorhombic $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} - 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is 18° . On closer examination of the curve will reveal that transition temperature will be $18^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. It will be further observed from the fig. 4, curve A where partition values in case of $3 \text{ CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host and Mn^{54} as guest has been plotted against temperature, a prominent break in the course of the curve is found in the neighbourhood of 31° . This break must, therefore, be due to the transition of the guest component. Transition temperature of $3 \text{ MnSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ s, therefore, $31^\circ \pm 2^\circ$. It should be mentioned that transition temperatures of orthorhombic $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $3 \text{ MnSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have never been determined by classical procedures.

It is of interest to mention that monoclinic heptahydrated vitriols which exists at ordinary temperature is likely to exist in orthorhombic forms at lower temperature. On closer examination of the solubility of monoclinic $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ we observed that the solubility with respect to temperature follows a straight line course from 0° onwards

Fig. 4.—On the study of the transition point of $3 \text{ MnSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with $3 \text{ CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host and Mn^{54} as guest.

Curve A.—Describes the partition values against temperatures.

Curve B.—Refers to time required for attainment of equilibrium between $3 \text{ CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host and Mn^{54} as guest.

N.B.—Concentration of cadmium in the saturated solution at 35° was $3.14M$ and that of natural manganese was $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ in $0.5N \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$.

upto the decomposition into lower hydrates. Transition temperature of the orthorhombic $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as determined by us is, however, 18° . Failure in its isolation is, therefore, due to the fact that it is metastable with respect to the stable monoclinic variety. It is quite likely that the orthorhombic variety exists side by side with the hexahydrate at this temperature. This finding has been derived from the fact that monoclinic $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ exists at $24.8^\circ \pm 0.3^\circ$ in equilibrium with the corresponding hexahydrate.

Amongst the vitriols $3 \text{ CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is well known. Existence of the corresponding hydrate in case of cobalt has been claimed through mixed crystal formation⁴. It was, therefore, of interest to derive evidence and to find out the transition point of these interesting series by the help of the method of approach as developed by us¹. $3 \text{ CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is the only host component for such study. It is also stable upto 41.5° . Mn^{54} was, therefore, chosen to derive evidence on the existence of $3 \text{ MnSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and to find out the transition point of this interesting compound. The partition value in this system is, however, very low. A glance at table-1(f, g) where a few typical data has been recorded will show that distribution coefficient comes out constant. This gives a strong evidence on the existence of thus far unknown $3 \text{ MnSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It has already been pointed out that (vide fig. 4, curve A) transition temperature of this compound is $31^\circ \pm 2^\circ$. Further it should be pointed out that no hydrates other than $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been reported to be stable above 27.7° ^{6,7}. Transition temperature of $3 \text{ MnSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as determined by us sets forth an evidence that it is probably metastable with respect to other hydrates of manganous sulphate including monohydrate.

In our previous study¹ we found that there are two varieties of monoclinic zinc sulphate. Each variety is mixed crystal forming with $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (monoclinic). Transition temperatures of these two varieties have been reported¹. In order to finding out whether such characteristic is common to all the vitriols we included the distribution study with $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host and Co^{60} as guest. Fig. 2 curve A will show that the same characteristic nature is observed in case of cobalt as well. Transition temperature of one variety is 30.5° and that of the other one is 47° .

It should be mentioned that by studying distribution coefficient with $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (monoclinic) we have observed two transition points both in case of zinc and cobalt as guest components. From the solubility of cobalt sulphate and that of ferrous sulphate at different temperatures it can be inferred that only one variety is stable. Probably the other variety which we are referring is metastable with respect to the stable variety. It is of interest to point out that zinc sulphate as guest also shows two transitions in case of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host. One form is well known to us and has also been isolated by workers³. Existence of the other form has been shown through distribution studies¹. It is to be noted that transition temperature of this metastable form lies in the neighbourhood of stable orthorhombic variety.

Before conclusion it is worth mentioning that the method of approach has enabled us to find out the transition temperature of two varieties of monoclinic vitriols in each case. It has also been possible to determine the transition temperature of orthorhombic $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and that of $3 \text{ MnSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ which was thus far unknown. It has been found that the procedure is valid with carrier-free isotopes and in finite concentration of the guest components where a chemical approach in ascertaining the distribution is feasible. The method, therefore, can be claimed to be a very good approach towards the investigation of thus far unknown cases where the conventional procedure can not give any success.

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4. H. Bassett and (Miss) I. Sanderson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1116
5. C. D. Carpenter and E. R. Jette, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 578.
6. H. Chihara and S. Seki, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1953, 26, 88.
7. J. W. Meller, "A Comprehensive treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. XII, p. 403. Longmans, Green and Co. (1957).